

DC-Loop Stray Inductance Characterization in Printed Circuit Board Using a Vector Network Analyzer

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Abstract

Stray inductance in the commutation loop causes oscillations that reduce power converter efficiency and increase electromagnetic noise. The fast switching of *Wide Band-Gap* (WBG) devices intensifies these effects. Accurate DC-loop inductance characterization is essential for design optimization and EMI modeling. This paper presents a method using incremental *Vector Network Analyzer* (VNA) measurements to isolate inductive contributions from the DC-link and *Printed Circuit Board* (PCB) without high-voltage testing. Applied to a GaN-based traction inverter, the approach enables pre-assembly analysis and effective switching characterization, offering a practical tool for improving system performance and reliability.

1 Introduction

Stray inductance in the DC loop contributes to voltage overshoot during transistor turn-off, which in turn generates electromagnetic noise and reduces overall system efficiency. This inductance can be split into several components (see Fig. 1):

Chip-related typically characterized by the chip manufacturer and available in the datasheet of the component;

Capacitor-related also specified by the manufacturer and available through datasheets and online resources;

PCB-related which varies by application and depends on the physical layout and geometry of traces and planes on the PCB and must therefore be measured directly on the actual hardware.

While various methods exist to measure the total loop inductance [1]–[4], they generally focus on characterizing the entire power stage. However, understanding the individual contributions to stray inductance is essential for optimizing design and compare different solutions. Since chip inductance is readily available from datasheets, this paper concentrates on measuring the capacitor- and

Fig. 1: DC-loop stray-inductance composition.

PCB-related inductance using a vector network analyzer (VNA). The results are then compared with traditional stray inductance values obtained from *Double-Pulse Test* (DPT) showing strong correlation.

2 Inductance Modeling

Stray inductance present in the DC-loop is generating voltage overshoot on power devices every time a commutation takes place. This has several effects on the system:

- Reduces the converter efficiency, since the voltage overshoot increases switching losses;

Fig. 2: Composition of the DC-link under exam.

- Produces stresses on the power transistors (e.g., voltage overshoots), mining the reliability of the whole converter;
- Generates higher electro-magnetic emissions.

For this reasons, limiting the stray inductance is beneficial when designing a power stage.

The inverter under exam uses GaN cascode devices from Nexperia [5] connected in parallel to reach the maximum current of 120 A peak. The DC-link has been sized to cope with the resulting ripple current (about 80 A) and to limit the maximum DC voltage drop to 20 V. The result was the usage of three film capacitors 70 μ F each [6]. The datasheet of these devices is declaring about 15 nH stray inductance per element, but their size makes almost impossible to connect them close enough to neglect the PCB contribution. To limit the PCB stray inductance, local ceramic capacitors have been added as shown in Fig. 2.

The estimation of these contribution is not straightforward and requires expensive electromagnetic solvers. For this reason, we preferred to characterize real samples and thus quantify the impact our design choices.

3 Measurements

The final layout has been measured using a VNA and then compared with the information that can be obtained from the classical DPT characterization, to verify the results.

3.1 VNA Characterization

Vector network analyzers are typically used to characterize device in the radio-frequency range, but since modern power transistors exhibit wide bandwidth performance, these instruments are becoming important to understand the circuit behavior up to several hundreds megahertz. The design under

Fig. 3: The *shunt-thru* measurement methodology.

Fig. 4: Characteristic impedance of VNA ports compared to typical stray DC-loop inductances.

exam in this paper is based on Nexperia GaN high-voltage cascode transistors [5] with fast slew-rates (i.e., 20 V/ns during switch-on and 45 V/ns during switch-off), leading to the requirement for the minimum acquisition bandwidth of

$$BW_{\min} = \frac{0.35}{\min(t_{\text{rise}}, t_{\text{fall}})} \approx 40 \text{ MHz}$$

since above that frequency the harmonic content is decreasing faster and it is typically neglected [7]. Nevertheless, the interinteraction between stray parameters (e.g., PCB stray inductance and transistors output capacitance) can generate resonances at higher frequencies that might be triggered during commutations and hence producing ringing beyond this theoretical limit. For this reason it is important to characterize the whole system at least up to 100 MHz.

From the experience matured in previous designs, the expected inductance is below 20 nH, hence providing a low impedance compared to the 50 Ω characteristic impedance of VNAs ports (Fig. 4). Theory states that the so-called *shunt-thru* measurement is the most suitable technique for low impedances [8]. This measurement requires to have the two ports connected in parallel to the De-

Fig. 5: PCB adaptation to perform *shunt-thru* measurement.

vice Under Test (DUT), as shown in Fig. 3. To realize this connection, the power stage has been modified as shown in Fig. 5. One of the power transistor is bypassed using a short-circuit and on the other the two measurement ports are connected. Starting from the setup shown in Fig. 5, a set of incremental measurements has been performed: first it has been characterized the PCB with film capacitors, then ceramic capacitors were added to understand the benefits introduced by these local, low-inductive elements. Next section is providing details about these two measurements.

3.1.1 Film Capacitor Only

The presence of bulky film capacitors is required for stabilizing the dc voltage while high current is provided to the load. Since three capacitors are put in parallel to reduce their *Equivalent Series Resistance* (ESR) and hence make the dc-link able to withstand to high current rates, the effect of the number of these devices has been characterized with the VNA measurement. Three separate measurements have been performed, adding a capacitor more at each measurement (Fig. 6). Acquisitions of these measurements have been processed as described in [9] and results are shown in Fig. 7. A single capacitor introduces a total stray inductance of

$$L_{1c} = ESL + L_{PCB,1} = 22 \text{ nH} \quad (1)$$

Since the device datasheet reports a typical *Equivalent Series Inductance* (ESL) of 15 nH, the PCB adds about 7 nH. Adding the second capacitor does not half the inductance, since it is more distant, hence the PCB introduces more stray inductance:

$$L_{2c} = (ESL_1 + L_{PCB,1}) \parallel (ESL_2 + L_{PCB,2}) \quad (2) \\ = 14.4 \text{ nH}$$

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 6: Measurement setup for film capacitors: 1 (a), 2 (b), and 3 (c) components assembled.

Fig. 7: Actual effect of adding multiple film capacitors in parallel on DC-loop stray inductance.

Fig. 9: Actual effect of adding multiple ceramic capacitors in parallel to the film capacitors.

Fig. 8: PCB adaptation to perform *shunt-thru* measurement with local ceramic capacitor added.

hence, PCB-related stray inductance can be derived as

$$\begin{aligned} (ESL_2 + L_{PCB,2}) &= 41.7 \text{ nH} \\ L_{PCB,2} &= 26.7 \text{ nH} \end{aligned}$$

The approach can be repeated for the third capacitor.

Due to the stray inductance introduced by the substrate, the combined effect of the three capacitors in parallel is a net reduction of the stray inductance by about 50% (from 22 nH to 11 nH) and not to 67% as it would be neglecting PCB contribution.

3.1.2 Adding Ceramic Capacitors

Going further with this incremental approach, ceramic capacitors have been added. The net benefit is provided by a much lower stray inductance (less than 1 nH each) and by the presence of multiple of these devices in parallel surrounding each switch pair. Moreover, these are closer than the film capacitors, minimizing the commutation loop size, hence reducing even further the stray inductance. Figure 8 shows the measurement setup.

The result of these measurements is visible on Fig. 9. The benefit is evident: stray inductance of film capacitors only (11.4 nH) is more than halved

Fig. 10: Vertical and horizontal commutation loops.

by ceramic capacitor inclusion (4.5 nH). This is specifically true in the range between 2 MHz and 100 MHz, where the inductance is almost constant. Since commutations have harmonics comprised into this range, this results extremely beneficial to limit undesired behaviors like voltage overshoots and ringing.

The introduction of the ceramic capacitors changes the DC-loop inductance from *vertical* (i.e., between film capacitor terminals) to *horizontal* (i.e., between ceramic capacitor rails) as Fig. 10 shows.

3.2 DPT Characterization

To validate the findings obtained using the VNA, stray inductance has to be measured with a differ-

Fig. 11: Voltage drop induced by current commutation on stray dc-loop inductance.

ent method. It is possible to extract the dc-loop stray inductance from the voltage drop visible during the current commutation (Fig. 11) and then compare it with the value obtained from the VNA characterization. Unfortunately, the impossibility to directly measure the current into the *Field-Effect Transistor* (FET) introduces uncertainty in the time of the current calculation, hence this method does not provide a very precise reference, but it is used to compare the VNA results and validate this method. The voltage drop is given by the classical inductance relationship

$$V_{\text{drop}} = L_s \cdot \frac{di_{\text{DS}}}{dt} \approx L_s \cdot \frac{\Delta i_{\text{DS}}}{\Delta t}$$

Using the values reported in Tab. 1 it is possible to calculate the stray inductance in different operating conditions. Even if affected by significant variability, these values are providing an average value of 5.9 nH. This measurement includes the whole DC-loop, i.e., the DC-link, the PCB, and the power device. The VNA characterization previously performed, instead, is only measuring the DC-link with the PCB, hence the stray inductance in the package is not included. Combining the results of these two analyses, it is possible to get

$$L_{\text{chip}} = L_{\text{DPT}} - L_{\text{VNA}} = 5.9 \text{ nH} - 4.5 \text{ nH} = 1.4 \text{ nH}$$

The comparison of this value with the one reported for the CCPAK1212 package (i.e., 1.2 nH [10]) provides a good alignment between the two characterization methodology used.

It is worth mentioning that the effect of the fixture has not been considered so far. This is because the length of the fixture is about 8 mm, about 1/6 of the dimension of the dc-loop, hence its contribution should be limited. To validate this statement and improve the measurement a de-embedding procedure shall be put in place [11]. This procedure is

Tab. 1: Value of stray inductance obtained from different methods.

Meas n.	ΔI , A	V_{drop} , V	Δt , ns	L_s , nH
1	25	13	10	5.2
2	30	13	14	5.6
3	35	14	16	6.0
4	40	14	19	6.3
5	45	15	20	6.3
6	50	15	20	6.0
7	55	15	20	5.8
Average L_s, nH				5.9

under definition and hence has not been included in this paper for lack of time, but will be included in a future publication.

3.3 Considerations

Previous sections showed the measurements performed with the VNA are confirmed by those coming from DPT characterization. But the former has some intrinsic valuable benefits:

- The VNA does not require high-voltage, hence the measurement can be performed in a safer and easier way compared to DPT;
- Measurements can be performed incrementally adding components on the bare PCB, allowing a more detailed characterization and generating the data for precise circuit models including stray parameters;
- Measurement can be used to characterize a PCB production batch, to intercept deviations and anomalies on the process;
- The data obtained can be used to create and tune electric models of the power stage to investigate further its behavior.

4 Conclusion

This paper described the usage of VNA to characterize the DC-loop of a custom power stage developed for a power inverter based on GaN transistors. The usage of the VNA has been explored to provide a broad band investigation of the stray inductance in the commutation loop and hence evaluate the benefit of using multiple capacitor devices with different technologies in the limitation of voltage overshoot. This measurement technique can have multiple advantages, since it does not require to have the whole power stage assembled and it does

not need to be operated at high voltage. The results are in-line with those obtained using classical DPT characterization, confirming this approach to be a valid alternative to this methodology.

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